
FORMATION OF NATIONAL IDENTITY IN KARAKALPAKSTAN TELEVISION CHANNELS

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ABSTRACT

This article explains the content and essence of nationalism in the programs and films of Karakalpakstan's state and non-state television channels, the general concepts of nationality and culture.

Keywords: TV channel, program, national costumes, values, culture, tradition, language.

The aspect of each country that distinguishes it from other nations is its nationality. The reason is that any country is distinguished from other nations by its nationality. Nationality is the heritage of our ancestors, our traditions, our common abilities, which we have followed for thousands of years. In today's globalization process, focusing on nationality is very important. The role of mass media in promoting these things is incomparable. Because any material presented to the public has an impact on the human mind, and concepts arise in relation to it. We can see this not only in social networks, but also in the prepared materials of state and non-state TV channels. The reason is that television has a special role in providing accurate and reliable information to people. [Television is a type of journalism that actively affects not only the human mind, but also his emotions. Television has become an incomparable fruit of human intelligence, a great achievement of science and technology, a universal result of human culture, and an incomparable factor in its further development]. For example, let's see the expression of nationalism in the example of Karakalpakstan television. It is the only state television in the Republic, which broadcasts news of various genres in an operational manner. Live broadcasts ensure the closeness of television and its audience. [The first program of the channel was broadcast on November 5, 1964. The programs are conducted in Karakalpak, Uzbek, Russian and languages. Air coverage is 95-98%.2] Now there is also a program in Kazakh language [It was broadcast in Karakalpak and Russian languages

a few minutes a day. In 1965, programs was broadcast four times a week for 2.5 hours. After the independence of Uzbekistan, Karakalpakstan television became part of Uzbekistan TRK (now Uzbekistan MTRK). Since 2002, the television and radio company of the Republic of Karakalpakstan has been established]. [From January 1, 1966, the length of the shows was increased to 3 hours, and the shows were broadcast every day of the week except Wednesday. Also, on weekends and holidays, from 12:00 noon, shows for children called "Jetkinshek is a guest at us", "Work wants to be brave", "Fishermen's children", "Poets for children" began to be shown. Thanks to the activities of the dubbing studio, which started working on June 1, 2013, young TV viewers had the opportunity to watch cartoons in Karakalpak language. In 2014, the second dubbing studio was launched, and films and television series were dubbed into Karakalpak language.

It broadcasts not only local news, but also the news of all over the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad in its programs. Currently, there are 48 programs and three editorials on television, and the materials are prepared in various genres. Among these programs, there are many programs that represent the nationality we mentioned. That is, the program "Assalawma aleykum, Karakalpakstan" is the morning program. It stands out for its in the videos and its presence on live broadcasts. The first broadcast was on July 1, 2002. Despite the fact that the duration of the show is now 80 minutes, the TV viewers can cheer up and learn more. The reason is that, firstly, interviews are held with guests from various fields, secondly, interesting films are made from each other. The program airs seven days a week. But everyday pictures are different. The reason is that on one day material is prepared on sports, health, reading, and another day museums, historical places, successful people, young people and so on. In addition, the guests of the show visit in various directions. The most interesting and important part of the program for the audience is the singing of national songs by bakshi, jirovs wearing Karakalpak national costumes. That is, it will be performed by them after the start of the show. Their performance in national costumes is considered to represent the nationality to the people in the first place. Then, the musicians who started the show with their live songs will be guests until the end of the program and will perform Karakalpak folklore songs, epics, and stories. By watching this and hearing the conversation, the audience can get more information about this field. The reason is that they also provide information on the origin epics and how they are performed.

We should mention that every bakshi who visits us as a guest comes with a national costume. These clothes are mainly decorated with national Karakalpak motifs. [The ancient karakalpak embroidery consisted of small pattern elements with different threads and a relatively large amount of dark red. The balance of different colors was a combination of red, brown, pistachio-green, and golden colors] . The clothes with this pattern symbolize the national identity of the Karakalpak people. In addition to the patterns, each of them has a cowl cap and girls' headwear has its unique characteristic. If the girl wears the skullcap with the right side, she is considered married, if she wears it with the left side, she is considered single. In addition, presenters wear national costumes on national holidays and special events. In this show, in the expression of national identity means not only the external appearance, but also the essence of the shows. For example, there is a "So'z qa'dri" broadcast, and its the general meaning is about proverbs. It is to test people's knowledge of Karakalpak folk proverbs. The filming process is not in the studio, but on the roads, in crowded places. Through this, people's interest in folk proverbs increases and they test their knowledge. This is also a kind of national identity. Because, there is special information about these proverbs in the 100 tom Karakalpak folklore.

Also, there is a "Tour to the Museum" broadcast, which provides information about the exhibits in the Igor Vitalyevich Savitsky Museum. The history of their creation. The most preserved place of nationality is the museum. Viewers will get a lot of information while watching it. In addition, we can learn about the preservation of nationality through other broadcasts. For example, they finde a native speaker on the topic of language and talk about the importance of mother language. Currently, it is possible to obtain information on the role and importance of the Karakalpak language in society. In this broadcast, the celebration of national holidays is involved in detail. Generally speaking, this program has many elements that express nationality. [Other than Karakalpakstan TV, there are also genres such as epic and terme genres performed by zhirau and bakshis, holiday programs, concerts and performances, which are hardly found on other televisions or do not fit into the traditional classification]

We should also mention that there is a program "Ata Miyras" which differs from other programs in terms of expressing nationality.

It is broadcast twice a month, and the guests are bakshi, jirov, girjekchi. Since this is a live program, studio guests will perform national folk songs requested by TV

viewers. The participants of this broadcast will also be in national clothes. Since the program is live, it has a high connection with TV viewers. There is also the show "Ulli Ziban", which is broadcast once a week. Bakshi and zhirau are guests in the show and perform folk epics. The difference between this and other broadcasts is that the filming process takes place mainly in "Qara u'y" (black house). [Among the people, it has names such as "black house", "white grass", "gray grass", "gray horde", and there are six, eight, twelve other names. "O'tov" ("Qara u'y) is made of durable, flexible willow. It is carried out in three steps - first kerege (wood, fence), then shan'araq (roof of a black house), and last step is uviq (pole)]

Filming process in "Qara u'y" gives us a little insight into those ancient times. In addition, national identity is depicted in "Yadnama" programm. The reason is that this broadcast provides information about the best results in the work of various professions. For example, that work of a writer who has written a good work. The writing of that book and the description of the events are also nationalistic. The reason is that in the events of those books, the life of the Karakalpak people is ruined. Or, if it is an artist's work, the same one makes it invisible in his work. In addition, non-state TV channels also have programs with similar content. For example, the programm "O'zligim" on Amudarya TV. This is a program that will be broadcast this year and will be broadcast seven times a week. Each episode of the show is different, but the purpose is the same, that is, to describe the nationality. In this show, the presenter is always wearing a national black hat.

In the background of the screen behind the presenter, there are pictures of two women wearing national costumes with national patterns. The show mainly provides detailed information about the national costumes of the people, the history and origin of the programs and national games. For example, in the very first episode of the show, it was told about the history of the Karakalpak women's headdress, that is, the purpose of which the girls wore it. In the next issues, information will be given about the traditions preserved among the people, how they are preserved today, and children's national games. And due to the fact that the dutor has been a national musical instrument in this nation for a long time, its history is discussed. It is different from other people's books because it has national patterns. It is a two-stringed, clicked instrument made of wood, with a pear-shaped body covered with a thin wooden cover, a short fingerboard, 12 13 extended frets. A three-stringed, bowed musical instrument with a gourd resonator and a leather cover is a companion to the girjek dutori. The symbol of the Karakalpak musical culture is the kobyz, a wooden

musical instrument with two strings, played with a bow, and an open resonator. During the show, various students will be explained through pictures and videos. In addition, the program "Jaslar life" of "Jaslar TV", which is considered a non-state TV channel, has a film "National Heritage" depicting nationality. In this, information is also given on Karakalpak national clothes, traditions, their origin, and their importance today. Moreover, the most interesting part of the show is the picture of young people in national costumes standing in the background of the presenter's speech. This is also a part of nationality.

Culture is considered the mirror of any nation, its role in society is special. Therefore, how to pass it on to the next generation depends on that country. The role of mass media in fully explaining these things to the people is incomparable.

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